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Mr.Ubale Amol Baban**

[AUTHOR : BINDU M.P.]

**A STUDY ABOUT THE LIFE SKILLS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS
OF KERALA****BINDU M.P.****UGC-JRF**

Govt. Brennen College Of Teacher Education
(Research And Course Work Centre In Education)

Thalassery, Kannur, Kerala-670101

Abstract

This article discusses the Life Skills of secondary school teachers. The study was conducted among secondary school teachers of five districts of Kerala. Normative survey was used for the study and data were collected using Life skill Assessment scale developed by the investigator. Stratified random technique was used to select sample. The study reveals that teachers have below average life skills.

INTRODUCTION

21st century requires individuals who are motivated as well as use higher level of cognitive to improve their life opportunities and to develop appropriate citizenship skills. This includes being involved to improve society and improving quality in human relations. Fast changing knowledge economics of modern times call for new core competencies among all teachers in the society. Skill development is important because of its contribution to enhancing

productivity at the individual and national level. Improvement of skill enhances professional competency and positive attitude towards worlds. The challenge of quality education for all children requires good teachers. Education provides a solid foundation to seed the multidimensional development of information and communication skills, thinking and problem solving skills. Life skills enrich people with knowledge and skills to improve lives and values and attitude to live together. The goal of any educational system is to ensure that targeted population to achieve progress and attain higher mental disposition related to thinking and reasoning abilities, life skills and values to participate and perform for progress and advancement of the society. Since life skills are closely related to psycho-social competency, teachers are supposed to have these skills for enhancing all-round development of the students.

Life skills is a group of psycho-social competencies and interpersonal skills that help people to make informed decisions, solve problems, think critically, creatively, communicate effectively, build healthy relationship, empathise with others and cope with and manage their lives in a healthy and productive manner. (WHO,1999).

A teacher that provides the right encouragement and direction to his or her students can actually help them into fine young individuals of tomorrow, by imparting values such as perseverance, hard work, determination and respect. The way teacher influences a child in his or her life, is different phases, let's take a look at how a teacher moves from being a guide to a mentor to a friend, to his/ her students in order to help them into capable of tomorrow. Therefore it is essential to know the life skills of teaches.

Defining Life Skills

Life skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. Described in this way, skills that can be said to be life skills are innumerable, and the nature and definition of life skills are likely to differ across cultures and settings. However, analysis of the life skills field suggests that there is a core set of skills that are at the heart of skills-based initiatives for the promotion of the health and well-being of children and adolescents. These are listed below:

- Decision making
- Problem solving
- Creative thinking
- Critical thinking
- Effective communication
- Interpersonal relationship skills
- Self-awareness
- Empathy
- Coping with emotions
- Coping with stress

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE

Teachers are the burning lamp for future generations. Teachers are the necessary instrument to reform education and to rescue the world through education. Teaching involves the articulation of so many skills and decision making process within the minimum possible time that is employed by majority of skilful teachers. Improving life skill of teachers is the corner stone of any worthwhile reformation in the field of education. The quality of education that goes on in an institution is depends upon the quality of teachers. A teacher who is so interested in his

profession is ready to improve his professional abilities and will be a committed teacher. A good teacher is one who able to inculcate in their students the keenness to observe and pay attention to learn and education involves learning from all possible sources of life. Teachers today has multifaceted role such as teaching, research management, Administration, counsellor, curriculum makers etc. therefore it is necessary to update the proficiency and competency of teachers for improving the quality of education. The quality of a nation depends upon the quality of nation and which intern depends upon the quality of education, which intern depends on the quality of teachers. Lots of research has been conducted on teaching profession, in which Sekar, G.Ranganathan (1988), found that most of the teachers were not satisfied with their nature of work, personal policies, salary, personal relations, achievement, relation with superiors and colleges, working conditions in schools. All these reflect in their profession hence skilful teacher is the need of the present day system of education, in which school is the miniature society.

A teacher is a psychological entity, an ensemble of numerous psychological characteristic such as ideas, thoughts, feelings, emotions, attitudes, needs and drives-highly complex and delicate to deal with. Majority of the teachers enter the teaching profession not with love for it, but due to several factors. The unfortunate position is that educated Indians take to teaching not for love for it, but because they have nothing better and nothing else for giving them as a livelihood. Professionalisms have its pressure and compulsion. They have to act as the agents of change and modernization, cultural reconstructions, and social development to earn recognition from society by acquiring new competencies and commitments. Hence the present study.

OBJECTIVES

- To know the life skills of teachers
- To know the life skills of teachers with respect to gender, type of subjects, and type of schools.

METHODOLOGY

Normative survey method was used for the study. The sample for the present study is 400 secondary school teachers in five districts of Kerala. The sample of the study has been selected by simple random sampling technique. The life skill assessment scale was constructed by the investigator (2013).

Sample

The present study was conducted on a representative sample of 400 teachers, drawn from four districts of Kerala. The sample was selected using stratified random sampling technique giving due representation to factors like gender, subjects opted for teaching and types of schools.

Tools

Life Skill Assessment Scale prepared by the investigator. The scale consists of 50 statements to measure the various aspects of life skills. The validity and reliability of the scale was established by item discrimination and T-R test method.

Statistical Techniques

Test of significance of difference in the mean score of large independent samples, t^2 - test.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table: 1 Life Skills of Secondary school teachers

Sample	N	Mean	S.D
Secondary School Teachers	400	88.64	12.54

Comparison of Mean Life skills Scores of Teachers for the Sub sample based on Gender, Subjects and Type of School

Summary of the Test of Significance of Difference between the Mean Life skills Scores of Teachers for the Sub sample based on Gender, Locale, Subjects and Type of School

Variables	Sub sample	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t
Gender	Male	200	45.7750	11.48013	.917
	Female	200	46.9100	13.21914	
Subjects	Arts	200	45.3000	11.77639	1.688
	Science	200	47.3850	12.89645	
Type of School	Government	200	48.5150	13.35257	3.561
	Aided	200	44.1700	10.927	

The mean Life skills scores of scores of male and female teachers are 45.77 and 46.91 respectively with standard deviation of 11.48 and 13.21. The calculated critical ratio obtained for the difference of mean life scores of male and female teachers .917, which is lower than the table value (1.96) for significance at 0.05 levels. Hence the difference between the mean scores of Life skills of male and female teachers is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels.

The mean Life skill scores of government and aided school teachers are 48.51 and 44.17 respectively with standard deviation of 13.35 and 10.92. The calculated critical ratio obtained for the difference of mean scores of Government and Aided school teachers is 3.561, which is higher than the table value (1.96) for significance at 0.05 level. Hence the difference between the mean Life skill scores of Government and Aided school teachers is statistically significant at 0.05 levels.

Mean Life skill scores of Arts and Science subjects teachers are 45.300 and 47.385 respectively. The calculated critical ratio obtained for the difference of mean scores on life skill of arts and Science teachers is 1.68 which is lower than the table value (1.96) for significance at 0.05 level. Hence the difference between the mean scores of Arts and Science teachers is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels.

RESULT AND FINDINGS

The study reveals that the mean Life skill scores of secondary school teachers are 88.64 and standard deviation 12.54. This shows that the teachers have below average life skills. It is found from the Table 1 that the Life skills of teachers are range from 45.775 to 46.910. From the Table: 2, it can be concluded that there is no gender difference exists in life skill assessment scale. Male and female teachers are equal in their life skills. When compared on the basis of type of school Government school teachers have high life skill than aided school teachers. As far as type of subject opted is concerned Science teachers have high life skill score than the Arts teachers.

CONCLUSIONS

A study show that life skill of secondary school teaches is below average. And there is difference among government and aided school teachers. Science teachers show high life skills than Arts teachers. There is a need for giving life skill training for teachers since life skills is an important component for psycho- social competencies. Life skill is essential to face the challenges of the day today life and need of schools. The real need in our school culture is to create and sustain learning environments that allow regular, skilled and authentic feedback for

student and teachers. Only skill full teachers can accept the change and responds positively to critical situations inside and out schools. Society expects some sorts of responsibility from the teachers to society. The need for life skills of the teacher to equip him with the necessary skills to impact knowledge and have confidence in his profession to lace global competitiveness is very critical. A school system's most important asset is its teaching force. It is widely recognised that although content, text books, buildings, equipment, laboratories, exam and testing systems are all important factors, learning result would be fairly useless if teachers did not know how to use the tools. A teacher with life skills become a competent and a complete teacher.

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